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**ECOLOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF NATURE MANAGEMENT IN THE
MODERN WORLD**

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ANNOTATION

The article describes the complex relationship between nature and society and some environmental problems that arise as a result of this, and also comments on the scientific and ecological foundations of environmental management.

Keywords: *biosphere, environment, natural resource, environmental management, human factor, environmental problems.*

It is known that since the birth of the human race on Earth, it has constantly changed its needs for life and economic activity at the expense of natural resources. At different stages of human development, the use of nature and the scale of anthropogenic pressure on it also varied. Historically, the changes that took place in the natural-geographical environment under the influence of the human factor were initially

uniform, but later, with the constant growth of the world's population, it is no secret that nature is becoming more and more anthropogenic, and the burden of human influence on it has increased. Moreover, since the second half of the twentieth century, the need for natural resources has increased sharply, and the satisfaction of this need by humanity, armed with modern equipment and technologies, thanks to the achievements of science, has created the basis for further expansion. the scale of environmental problems. Today, the environmental situation, which is becoming increasingly urgent, shows that it is now necessary to take into account the environmental factor when rationally using natural resources. First of all, this consists in protecting the environment, increasing the production of environmentally friendly non-waste products, and implementing a socio-economically oriented environmental policy. This process is quite complex, complex and expensive. However, it will be impossible to achieve environmental stability if they are not gradually introduced into the economy. From this point of view, the formation of deep knowledge and skills about the scientific, environmental and geographical foundations of environmental management is of great importance in the transition to sustainable economic development.

The general public recognizes that one of the most pressing problems of our time is optimizing the interaction between nature and society. This process is especially clearly manifested in the constant increase in the exchange of matter and energy between them. In particular, this phenomenon is aggravated due to changes in the natural energy balance as a result of human economic activity, the introduction of many natural resources into the economy, a sharp increase in the volume of industrial and municipal waste and their return to nature, the rapid use of natural resources, the ability to regenerate in process and features of cleaning from released waste.

In the conditions of rapid development of scientific and technological development, complex total problems of the relationship between nature and society have not yet been fully studied theoretically. At first glance, such a conclusion seems unfounded, since many natural sciences have been dealing with environmental

problems for a long time, but, nevertheless, the consequences of many undesirable natural processes and their causes, physical and chemical of an anthropogenic nature, are negative. The impact of factors on ecosystems has not yet been fully studied. The development of mining, construction and other projects, the development of arid lands, the widespread use of pesticides and chemical fertilizers in agriculture, the monopolization of certain crops, large-scale reclamation measures to combat undesirable natural phenomena - its absence causes processes unexpected for society. Intensification of extensive use of natural resources and ignoring long-term technical and economic efficiency often complicates the interaction between nature and society, the economic consequences of which are estimated in very large numbers.

Such errors are often caused by the difficulty of accurately predicting the “reverse impact” of the natural environment in relation to anthropogenic impact, the lack of scientifically based methods for assessing the acceptable level of human activity when using natural resources, and environmental protection tasks due to a limited understanding of the scientific nature of the conflicts that arise between the rapid use of resources. The interaction of humanity with nature is expressed very clearly and is controlled by certain laws. To the extent that human economic activity is compatible with the laws of nature in society, this activity is considered positive for society, and vice versa, if this creates an inverse proportionality to the laws of nature, then due to the development of various natural processes, alarming situations will arise for society. According to Nikolaev, all of nature (including society) consists of an integral system in which individual phenomena are organically connected with each other and form a single whole.

Nature is a whole, it includes countless different forms that exist in relationships. One of the fundamental laws of nature is the law of unity of the existing material system and the external conditions surrounding it. In relation to society, this is its unity with the geographical environment. Existence, space, or rather nature and society in which we live, is an integral and extremely complex system caused by the exchange of matter, energy and information. As a phenomenon changes in nature, other phenomena

associated with it also require changes in the same order. If the interaction between them is strongly expressed, then it affects events in territories adjacent to one local area. According to I.K. Nazarov, there is no rest in nature, it is always in motion and in various changes. It is for this reason that it is advisable for scientists to pay great attention to new phenomena, because they can greatly change the natural environment and neighboring complexes in the processes of emergence, formation and development.

One of the conditions for rapid changes in the natural environment is the law of diversity of landscapes (geosystems). Many experts recognize that there is a certain connection between the development of society and the diversity of nature. It has been established that if the natural conditions and resources of the region are diverse, favorable conditions will be created for the development of society. On the contrary, given the same natural conditions and resources of the territory, there will not be enough opportunities for the development of productive forces. In this context, the law of material systems and the environment and the law of landscape diversity operate simultaneously. In areas with a complex landscape structure, natural geographical conditions lead to intense environmental changes. That is why, in many cases, changes in natural (ecological) conditions are observed over large areas in accordance with the law of compatibility of processes in mutual movement.

It is worth noting that until the middle of the 20th century, the relationship between society and nature was more balanced than in subsequent years, since at that time the use of nature corresponded to needs. In subsequent years, the preservation of extensive environmental management led to an imbalance in the relationship between society and nature. Because due to the large-scale human impact on the environment, not only positive changes arise in the relationship between nature and society, but also negative consequences for humans, changes in the biosphere, ecological balance, environmental pollution and impoverishment of nature. Since the second half of the 20th century, when the level of environmental management has increased, the self-cleaning and control properties of the natural environment have been decreasing. In

this situation, nature has lost its resources and ability to restore ecological balance. We can conclude that in the process of rapid use of resources, nature loses the necessary properties. In this situation, the adverse effects of nature increase in scale and negative consequences begin to appear. This is seen as environmental stress and destruction, the enormous economic and social consequences of which are obvious to all.

References:

1. Akramova P. A. Ecological situation and its impact on the level of health of the younger generation. "O‘zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar" jurnali. Materiallari to‘plami 20 – janvar, 2022 - yil 4 – son. 98-102 bet
2. Uzbekistan. Reviews of environmental performance. United Nations, 2020. Geneva.
3. Third National Communication of the Republic of Uzbekistan under the UNFCCC. Tashkent 2016.
4. Report of the Center for Hydrometeorological Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan (UZHYDROMET) 2022 Bukhara.